

DELIVERABLE D2.1 – COLOSSE

HR Strategy

Project Acronym	COLOSSE
Project Full Name	Central European Platform for Plasma-Enabled Surface Engineering
Grant Agreement No.	101158464
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-04
Type of action	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Project starting date	1 April 2024
Project duration	36 months
Deliverable number	D2.1
Deliverable name	COLOSSE HR Strategy
Work Package	WP2
Type	R – Document, report
Main author	B. Wahlová, Z. Hrabovská
Lead beneficiary	Masaryk University
Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Due Date	September 2024
Date	27. 09. 2024
Version	1.0

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101158464. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

Abbreviations.....	4
Executive summary	5
Key words.....	5
1 Background.....	6
2 Objectives	7
3 Target Group.....	8
4 Recruitment and Selection of Researchers	9
5 Onboarding of Researchers (Preboarding, First day at Work, Adaptation).....	14
6 Training of Researchers and Research Support Staff.....	18
7 Conclusion.....	22
8 Attachments	22
Attachment 1: COLOSSE Job Advertising Template	23
Attachment 2: The European Competency Framework for Researchers.....	25
Attachment 3: COLOSSE Key Competencies Template.....	30
Attachment 4: COLOSSE Training Need Questionnaire Survey Template	35
Attachment 5: COLOSSE Training Topics Template.....	42
Attachment 6: COLOSSE Career Development Plan Template	43
Attachment 7: COLOSSE Training Feedback Form.....	46

Abbreviations

CDPs – Career Development Plans

CU – Comenius University

EU – European Union

HE – Horizon Europe

HR – Human resources

HRS4R – Human Resources Strategy for Researchers

ICDPs – Individual Career Development Plans

MSCA – Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

MUNI – Masaryk University

OTM-R – Open, transparent and merit-based recruitment

R1 – First Stage Researcher

R2 – Recognised Researcher

R&I – Research and innovation

UWB – University of West Bohemia

WP – Work package

Executive summary

The document presents the Human Resources Development Strategy aimed at addressing HR challenges in plasma-enhanced surface engineering, building on the existing HR strategies (HRS4R) of three COLOSSE centers.

This HR Development Strategy serves as a guide for improving HR practices in the COLOSSE centers, ensuring the recruitment and growth of international talent, and strengthening the overall research capabilities within the plasma-enhanced surface engineering sector.

Key words

Human resources, HRS4R, strategy, recruitment, onboarding, training, researcher, postdoc, competencies, career development plan

1 Background

Masaryk University (MUNI), Comenius University Bratislava (CU) and University of West Bohemia (UWB) (referred as “COLOSSE centres”) are all signatories of the European Charter & Code for Researchers, they hold the HR Excellence in Research Award and implement the HR Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R). The implementation status of HRS4R among these partners varies, depending on when they initially received the Award and their subsequent milestones.

All the COLOSSE centres are comprehensive universities – their disciplinary range is very broad. Yet, there are some specific HR challenges shared more particularly among research centres in the area of applied physics.

The COLOSSE Human Resources Development Strategy (referred as “The HR Strategy”), will provide an extra layer of detail to the institutional strategies to specifically address research in plasma-enhanced surface engineering, with potential to be transposed into broader areas of applied physics / plasma physics / engineering.

The COLOSSE Human Resources Development Strategy consists of

- A. COLOSSE Strategy for Recruitment and Onboarding of International Postdoctoral Researchers
- B. COLOSSE Strategy for Training of Researchers and Research Support Staff

The COLOSSE Human Resources Development Strategy is in line with following regulations:

- European Charter & Code for Researchers:
 - ✓ [New European Charter for Researchers 2023](#)
 - ✓ [COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION of 18 December 2023 on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe, \(C/2023/1640\)](#)
 - ✓ [The European Charter for Researchers & The Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers 2005](#)
- The European Competency Framework for Researchers
 - ✓ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en
 - ✓ <https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7da29338-37bf-4d51->

[b5eb-a1571b84c7ad_en?filename=ec_rtd_research-competence-presentation.pdf](#)

- Masaryk University guidelines:
 - ✓ [Masaryk University Selection Procedure Regulations](#)
 - ✓ [Recruitment Procedure at SCI MU \(OTMR Policy\)](#)
 - ✓ Recruitment Process Guidelines at SCI MU (OTM-R Practice, for internal access only)
 - ✓ [Onboarding Process at SCI MU](#)
 - ✓ [Education and Development of Employees at SCI MUNI](#)
 - ✓ [Strategy for Education and Support of Early-stage Researchers at SCI MUNI](#)
 - ✓ [System of Positions and Job Titles at SCI MUNI](#)
 - ✓ [Career Code at SCI MUNI](#)
- Comenius University guidelines:
 - ✓ [Recruitment Policy at the Comenius University](#)
 - ✓ [Mentoring Programme for Academics](#)
- University of West Bohemia guidelines:
 - ✓ [Principles of Open, Transparent and Merit-Based Recruitment at the University of West Bohemia](#)
 - ✓ [University Career Development Plan](#)

The Recruitment, Onboarding and Training objectives and principles described below are prepared in cooperation with all the COLOSSE centres. They are synergized and promoted together.

2 Objectives

Recruitment and Onboarding of International Researchers:

The Strategy for Recruitment and Onboarding of International Postdoctoral Researchers

is formed to establish a framework for the effective recruitment (attraction, selection, hiring) and onboarding of international researchers at the COLOSSE centres. Therefore, this document is divided into two specific sections: Recruitment

and Onboarding. In both of these sections, strategic goals are identified, which will be further implemented at the COLOSSE centres.

Training of Researchers and Research Support Staff:

The Strategy for Training of Researchers and Research Support Staff is formed to establish a comprehensive framework for the effectively identifying the key competencies required for the primary target group positions, assessing specific training needs, and ensuring Career Development Plans for these positions. This strategy will guide the organization of three training events for researchers and support staff (one at each COLOSSE partner institution), aimed at enhancing soft and transferable skills. Additionally, it will support the planning of two retreats for early-stage researchers as part of Work Package 3 of the COLOSSE project, “Develop skill-set that enables interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration and facilitates creativity”. Within the Training Strategy, strategic goals are also identified, which will be further implemented at the COLOSSE centers.

3 Target Group

International Researchers at COLOSSE Centres:

Early-Stage Researchers (Early-Career Researches) include graduates of doctoral programs from international universities who received their PhD degrees within the past eight years, as well as experienced and accomplished postdocs from foreign institutions. These individuals have a demonstrated interest in applied physics and are seeking to advance their careers.

In general, the Early-Stage Researchers are recognised as researchers in the initial stages of their research career including the research training – mainly PhD students, postdoctoral researchers. In detail, according to the [European Commission classification](#), these typically fall under:

R1 - First Stage Researcher: Researchers before obtaining a PhD degree, doing research under supervision up to the point of a PhD or equivalent level of competency and experience. Examples of occupations for researchers across sectors - doctoral candidate, junior academic, junior research analyst, junior research engineer, junior researcher/scientist, junior scientific officer, research apprentice/intern

R2 - Recognised Researcher: Researchers, PhD holders shortly after obtaining the degree, with a PhD or equivalent level of competency and experience who have not yet established a significant level of independence in developing their own research, attracting funding, or leading a research

group. Examples of occupations for researchers across sectors – junior academic, junior lecturer, junior research analyst, junior research engineer, junior researcher/scientist, junior scientific officer, postdoctoral researcher.

Among the individual COLOSSE partners, the titles and positions associated with R1 and R2 vary, encompassing roles such as PhD student, doctoral candidate, researcher (I and II), academic researcher (I and II), research specialist, junior researcher, postdoc, and postdoctoral researcher. All of these positions are included within the primary target group of the COLOSSE project."

In addition to the primary target group, consisting of Early-Stage Researchers, the Training activities will also be aimed at a broader audience within the **Research Support Staff**. This includes positions of Research Managers, who play a crucial role in overseeing research projects and ensuring their successful execution; Research Administrators, who handle the administrative and regulatory aspects of research activities; and Technical Support Staff, who provide essential technical assistance and maintenance of research equipment and infrastructure."

4 Recruitment and Selection of Researchers

4.1. Principles and Goals

Selection procedures are conducted in accordance with the following principles based on OTM-R (open-transparent-merit-based recruitment):

- **Openness** – job vacancies are advertised so as to be accessible to all candidates and to address the widest possible range of potential candidates.
- **Transparency** – selection procedure is simple and clear. Candidates outside of COLOSSE centres have the same access to information about selection procedure as those employed in COLOSSE centres.
- **Merit-based candidate evaluation** – candidates' evaluation is based on clear and objective criteria which ensure that the most suitable candidate is selected for the job by an independent and trained selection committee.
- **Equal opportunities** – any expression of discrimination or unequal treatment in the selection procedure is unacceptable. The selection procedure is conducted with respect to all candidates, taking into account the specifics of various social groups and respecting the candidates' specific requirements following from a disability or other disadvantage.
- **Efficiency** – selection procedures are held without undue delay and

represent a minimum administrative burden for the candidates and the selection committee. Electronic communication and documentation means are preferentially used in selection procedures.

- **Gender balance** – a reasonable gender balance of the selection committee is ensured in selection procedures, gender stereotypes in the evaluation of candidates are excluded.
- **Protection of rights** – selection procedures include the mechanisms for evaluation and quality control as well as procedures for submitting motions to investigate their course and results.

The goal of the COLOSSE Recruitment Strategy is to ensure open, transparent and merit-based recruitment (OTM-R) in international environment in order to select the most suitable international candidates in plasma-enhanced surface engineering area and expand the research teams with relevant experts and high-quality researchers.

Sub-goals:

- Ensure a professional, effective and transparent recruitment and selection process to find the most suitable candidates for open positions.
- Recruit highly talented Early-Stage Researchers from around the world.
- Promote international collaboration and knowledge exchange.

4.2. Scheme

4.2.1. Preparation of the Selection Procedure

- **Hire Request Specification**

COLOSSE centres have created a template for advertising open positions.

The advertising template, see Attachment 1 of this document, contains all the necessary information for candidates and selection committee members and reflect the principles of the European Charter and the Code:

- ✓ The advertising template is clear and concise.
- ✓ The advertising template clearly specifies number of open positions, expected start date, workplace (including the receiving lab), contract type, remuneration, the European Researcher Profile (R1, R2) and the application deadline.
- ✓ The requirements for the specific postdoctoral position are defined transparently and must not contain discriminatory criteria based on nationality, gender, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, language, religion or belief, political or other opinion, disability, age or sexual orientation.
- ✓ The requirements for the specific postdoctoral position define the necessary hard skills and soft skills, experience, and qualifications needed for successful job performance.
- ✓ The advertising template specifies necessary documents required from candidates, with the intention to minimise the administrative burden of candidates.
- ✓ The advertising template includes hyperlink referring to the recruitment process description of the advertising COLOSSE centre, including eventual complaint mechanism, or the recruitment process description itself, and a contact person for more detailed inquiries.
- ✓ The advertising template includes hyperlink referring to information on working conditions in the location, relocation support for international staff and description of career development opportunities of the advertising COLOSSE centre.

- **Sourcing**

In order to identify potential candidates, the COLOSSE centres plan to search in academic networks, industry partnerships, attend international conferences and workshops in plasma physics, materials science, and related fields to network with potential candidates, highlighting the benefits and opportunities of the postdoctoral positions offered.

The following **SOURCING CHANNELS** are used to advertise open postdoctoral positions:

- ✓ **University official noticeboards**, university (or faculty) career websites
- ✓ [Euraxess.com](https://www.euraxess.com) profile of the advertising COLOSSE centre equipped with the HR Excellence in Research Award logo
- ✓ [LinkedIn](https://www.linkedin.com) or similar platform profile of the advertising COLOSSE centre
- ✓ **Academic&Research job boards, e.g.:**
 - www.researchgate.net
 - www.nature.com/naturecareers
 - www.researchjobs.cz
- ✓ **Social media channels** to promote an opportunity and reach a wider audience of qualified candidates
- ✓ Dedicated webpages of the individual COLOSSE centres and the **COLOSSE website** with detailed information about the position and the application.

4.2.2. Progress of the Selection Procedure

- **Notifying all candidates about their application**

All candidates are informed of the submission of their documents at this phase. They are also informed of the further progress of the selection procedure, the date of the interviews and any other requirements or deadlines. Additionally, all candidates are informed of the result in the end of the selection process.

- **Establishing Selection Committees**

The type of open position is taken into account when a selection committee is being established. When appointing the selection committee members, aspects such as the professional profile, research experience and gender balance are taken into account. All the COLOSSE centres should establish a selection committee comprising experts in plasma physics, materials science, and related disciplines to review applications. Committee members are adequately trained in the recruitment rules.

- **Pre-screening of Received Applications**

The members of the selection committee, headed by the chairperson, will pre-select candidates from all applications received in the selection procedure based on specified selection criteria and prepare a list of candidates to be invited for an online interview. The committee carefully evaluates candidates' resumes, cover letters, recommendation letters, and publications in line with the OTM-R principles.

- **Evaluation of Candidates (interviews)**

During the second round of the selection process, online structured interviews take place with candidates who have met the basic conditions in the first round and have been identified as suitable candidates. Effective recruitment should be measurable. Therefore, the committee chooses key objective criteria aligned with the goals and expectations of the position. The committee usually evaluates the candidates based on their academic credentials, research experience, publications, and potential contributions to the field. The committee conducts online interviews to assess candidates' communication skills, research interests and compatibility with the research team. The result of the committee's discussion is a decision on the ranking of successful candidates and on the unsuccessful candidates, including the justification for not recommending them for the position. Subsequently, the selection committee headed by chairperson, decides on the selected candidate to whom a job offer will be sent.

4.2.3. Closure of the Selection Procedure

- **Issuing a job offer to the selected candidate**

The selection committee chairperson informs the HR department of the respective COLOSSE centre about the selection committee decision and provides details for issuing the official job offer in line with the centre's official pre-boarding process.

The job offer contains following items:

Job Title and Job Description, Start Date, Duration of Employment, Working hours, Probation Period, Place of Work, Monthly Gross Salary and additional benefits.

- **Informing unsuccessful candidates**

All candidates who apply receive feedback on whether they have been successful in the selection process:

- ✓ If they have not been selected for an interview, they will receive at least an email thanking them for applying.
- ✓ If they have not been selected in an interview process, they will receive at least an email thanking them for participation in the interview and ideally also a personal phone call from a selection committee chairperson.

In line with the principle of transparency, the unsuccessful candidates can request information on the strengths and weaknesses of their applications. This feedback is provided solely by the selection committee chairperson or the potential supervisor.

- **Deleting candidates' personal data**

It is the obligation of the organisation to deal with the personal data provided by

the candidates in the selection procedure in line with the GDPR rules, especially to ensure a complete deletion of all the materials provided by the candidates.

All participants in the selection procedure, i.e., selection committee members, HR Generalists/appointed administrative employees are obliged to remove all the materials intended explicitly for the purpose of the selection panel, immediately after the selection procedure concludes, and must not use these materials in any way any further.

5 Onboarding of Researchers (Preboarding, First day at Work, Adaptation)

5.1. Principles and Goals

The onboarding process aims to provide new employees with comprehensive support to ensure a smooth, administratively correct, and comfortable start. It helps them adapt effectively to the new working environment, navigate their probation period, and successfully complete the initial training.

The probation period serves two purposes: The new employee can make sure that his/her expectations of the position and job duties are met, and from the employer's perspective, the new employee's skills are adequate and that he/she is a good fit.

The goal of the COLOSSE Onboarding Strategy is to develop comprehensive onboarding program for international researchers including support for the visa process, housing, introduction to the research group and ensuring mentoring for postdocs to help them with their career development.

Sub-goals:

- Pay sufficient attention to onboarding of new employees, choose the appropriate mentor and provide feedback during the onboarding process.
- Encourage networking and collaboration among postdocs with each other and with other researchers at the institution.
- Retain highly talented Early-Stage Researchers from around the world.

5.2. Preboarding Administration and Logistics

5.2.1. Scheme

5.2.2. Preparing Contract and Employment Related documents

Once the selected candidate accepts the job offer, the COLOSSE centre prepares the employment contract and other related documents. The candidate/new employee signs these documents on the first day at work.

5.2.3. Initiation of Visa & Immigration Assistance and Relocation Support

All Colosse centres have a dedicated Welcome Office which is prepared to assist selected candidates with visa applications, work permits, and other immigration-related procedures. This office provides guidance and support throughout the visa process to ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and facilitate timely arrival and integration.

The Welcome Office also addresses the practical relocation inquiries and needs of incoming international employees and, when applicable, their family members. This service supports new hires and their families in adjusting to their new location by identifying and addressing their specific relocation requirements in accordance with the policies and resources of the respective centre.

Tip: To ensure the smooth adaptation of international staff, it is important that the receiving workplace provides comprehensive relocation support. This includes assistance with finding accommodation, temporary housing arrangements, support for family members, and communication with state authorities.

5.2.4. Preparing the Workplace

Once receiving the notification of a job offer acceptance by the candidate, the workplace initiates everything necessary for the new colleague addressing both logistical arrangements and work-related details. The supervisor or the workplace's designated person ensures all the required steps are carried out before the start date. The adaptation plan, including the mentor/buddy assignment for the new employee, shall be prepared. The mentor/buddy's role is to assist the new employee, familiarize him/her with the new working environment, or advise when handling job tasks. The new employee is informed about the first-day schedule by supervisor or the workplace's designated contact person.

Tip: To ensure the smooth adaptation of international staff, it is important that the receiving workplace is inclusive and has adopted English as a second language for communication, with the necessary infrastructure and support staff in place. It is also important that the receiving workplace offers high-quality working conditions and excellent technical equipment, as well as good coffee (for free) and a pleasant area for colleagues to sit and socialize.

5.3. First Day at Work and Adaptation

5.3.1. Scheme

5.3.2. First Day of Work

- **Welcome Email, Onboarding Plan**

Each new employee receives a special welcome email including overview of instructions and useful links related to new hire orientation. The employee also receives a printed or e-version of onboarding plan and shall be acquainted with the content.

- **Familiarization with Workplace, General Workplace Safety Training**

Within the first day at work, every new employee undergoes general workplace training and supervisor or mentor provides introduction in practical institutional and workplace-related matters.

- **Help with Residence and Practicalities**

Welcome office provides a list of steps, which the new international employee is obliged to do for the first days/weeks in terms of residence and practicalities. The office is able to help and advise all employees as well as their family members, with a range of related issues, such as arranging a Czech/Slovak bank account, collecting residence card, finding a general practitioner and other. It is also prepared to offer language courses or resources to improve communication and integration within the research team and broader community.

Tip: To ensure the smooth adaptation of international staff, it is important that the receiving workplace communicates openly, in personalized manner and provides comprehensive information about the workplace. Additionally, sending a welcoming email with the newcomer's photo to all staff can create a warm and inclusive atmosphere.

5.3.3. During Adaptation

- **Orientation in Work Tasks, Training**

Each new international employee will be assigned a mentor to support the integration process and provide ongoing guidance and feedback. Mentor will provide new employee with an initial training plan to get him/her familiarized with the institution's policies, facilities, and research protocols. This should also help to facilitate networking opportunities and help foreign researchers connect with peers and build professional relationships within the research community. As part of the integration process, the new international employee will also receive a Career Development Plan that includes training identified through the COLOSSE Training Strategy.

- **Familiarization with the Internal Information and Regulations**

New employees will receive a practical information (eventually employee guide) created especially for those who are newcomers.

The aim of this step is to support newcomers' orientation in the new work environment and provide useful information about university/faculty, employee care, practical operational matters or important internal regulations.

5.3.4. Before Onboarding Is Ended

- **Interview with the Employee, Evaluation of Adaptation**

At the end of onboarding (before the end of a probation period), it is essential for the employee's further work performance and career management to set up working conditions, development activities, and regular employee evaluation. An interview between the employee and the supervisor takes place, the aim of which is to give mutual feedback on whether the employee has enough information to take over the assigned agenda independently. The interview should provide the employee with additional support and provide training opportunities for next period.

6 Training of Researchers and Research Support Staff

6.1. Principles and goals

The goal of the COLOSSE Training Strategy for Researchers and the Support Staff is to identify the required key competencies, assessing specific core training needs, and preparing Career Development Plans for Researchers and Support Staff consensually for all three partners. This strategy will guide the organization of three training events for researchers and support staff (one at each COLOSSE partner institution), aimed at enhancing soft and transferable skills. Additionally, the strategy will support the planning of two retreats for Early-stage researchers.

Sub-goal:

- Distil the specific training needs and opportunities relevant to the field of plasma-enabled surface engineering from the general level of HR strategies at the involved partners.
- Actively work with supervisors to promote career development of Early-stage researchers by training in important soft, scientific and technical skills. Plasma-enabled surface engineering is a research area on the borders of disciplines – chemistry, physics, mathematics – and has some very good exploitation potential. Researchers in the area need to be able to combine and coordinate a wide range of scientific and technological approaches; and communicate also outside of the academic environment.

6.2. Scheme

6.3. Identification of Key Competencies

The aim is for the three COLOSSE partners to map and identify the key competencies required for developing soft skills, transferable skills, including technical and scientific skills, for the specified target group.

These competencies are formalized in **the Attachment 3: COLOSSE Key Competencies Template**.

The competency mapping results will be used to assess training needs of the target group by identifying skill gaps. This will then guide the selection of specific training topics and the creation of COLOSSE Career Development Plans for Researcher positions (R1-R2) and Support Staff positions.

The COLOSSE partners have varying levels of definition for positions, roles, and the associated skills and competency models. Therefore, the Training Strategy is structured as a general framework for competency mapping by the three COLOSSE partners. This framework is based on:

[European Competency Framework for Researchers](#), detail see in Attachment 2

[System of Positions and Job Titles at SCI MUNI](#), namely its Annexes 5 and 6, Competency models.

[CARDEA Competency Framework for Research Managers](#)

[ARMA UK Research Manager Competency Toolkit](#)

TIP: For the future tuning up the training plans it is recommended to use the [Era Talent Platform - Research and Innovation Careers Observatory \(ReICO\)](#)

6.4. Assessing Core Training Needs

Based on the competencies identified for the target group in line with the COLOSSE specifics, **gaps in skills and knowledge are determined using the following sources:**

- The **onboarding process** for new employees, which is managed by the employee supervisor.
- Identified **gaps in skills and knowledge** in relation to the key competencies outlined in step 6.3, as **assessed by the employee supervisor**.
- A **questionnaire survey conducted among the target group** of employees, following the structure provided in the **Attachment 4, Training Need Questionnaire Survey Template**.
- **Regular evaluation of employees' performance and work behaviour**, also under the supervision of the employee's direct manager.

This approach ensures a comprehensive assessment of the current capabilities within the team, facilitating targeted training interventions that address the identified deficiencies.

Tip: Use the following questions to guide the assessment

What are the current competencies of the researcher? What are the competencies required for their current/future research role? What specific training topics would address the identified gaps? Which competencies should be prioritized in the training programs?

6.5. Specifying Training Topics

The outcome of the identification of key competencies and the Training Needs Assessment is a **structured list of suggested training topics or areas for development** tailored to the specific needs of the target group. The identified training topics are formalized in the **Attachment 5: COLOSSE Training Topics Template**.

The template structure categorizes these topics according to the type of position,

ensuring that the training is aligned with the identified gaps in competencies and is relevant to the employees' roles and future career development.

6.6. Preparing Career Development Plans

Based on the outcomes from the Identification of Key Competencies, the Training Needs Assessment, and the Specification of Training Topics, Career Development Plans (CDPs) are prepared for each Position Type within the COLOSSE target group. These plans may also be tailored to individuals, resulting in Individual Career Development Plans (ICDPs). The responsibility for creating these plans lies with the individual supervisors.

To facilitate the creation of these plans, supervisors can use the provided template in Attachment 6: Career Development Plan Template.

Alternatively, the official Horizon Europe MSCA Career Development Plan (CDP) form can be used. This form is specifically tailored to the Horizon Europe framework and ensures compliance with the standards set by the European Commission. It can be accessed through the following links:

- [Horizon Europe MSCA CDP Form Overview](#)
- [Direct Download of the Career Development Plan Template](#)

6.7. Implementing the Training Strategy

Within the COLOSSE Work Package 3, “Develop skill-set that enables interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration and facilitates creativity”, based on the Specification of Training Topics, one training event at each of the COLOSSE centres to support **development of Soft** (such as communication, collaboration, critical thinking, entrepreneurial mindset), **Technical and Scientific and Transferable** (such as academic or grant writing, digital skills, presentation) **skills**. The trainings on non-scientific skills are intended as 2-4 day events for 15-20 participants. Consensual decision of partners on the actual topic of each training will be made upon the needs assessment done.

Further on, all the training and career development areas will be combined in the concept of **young researchers' retreats**. The retreats will bring together especially doctoral candidates and postdoc from the COLOSSE centres (strategic partners might be invited to join the events) for a 3-5 day programme including both scientific discussions on research topics brought in by the participants and training sessions. Young researchers will be actively engaged in preparation of the programme of the retreats. Each retreat is expected to be attended by 25-50 researchers.

6.8. Evaluating Quality of The Training

To ensure continuous improvement, after each training session, the satisfaction and overall experience of attendees with the quality of the training is be evaluated through a feedback questionnaire, administered via Microsoft Forms. A hyperlink to the questionnaire will is sent to participants via email shortly after the completion of the training. This survey will collect valuable insights into the effectiveness of the training content, the trainer's performance, and added value of the training.

For a detailed template of the feedback questionnaire, please refer **to Attachment 7: COLOSSE Training Feedback Form**. The gathered feedback is be analysed to identify areas for improvement in future training sessions, ensuring that the training program remains responsive to the evolving needs of the participants and continues to meet high-quality standards.

7 Conclusion

An effective Strategy for recruiting, onboarding and training of international researchers and training of the research support staff is crucial for achieving research and educational goals in the area of plasma-enabled surface engineering. By implementing the principles above, the COLOSSE centres can attract and retain top talents from around the world and promote COLOSSE facilities as excellent and reliable partners for research & Innovation.

8 Attachments

Attachment 1: COLOSSE Job Advertising Template

Postdoctoral Positions in the Field of Plasma Physics

Department of, Faculty of, University, is looking for talented **international candidates for Postdoctoral positions in the field of plasma-enabled surface engineering**. This unique opportunity will be funded through Horizon Europe project COLOSSE (Central European Platform for Plasma-Enabled Surface Engineering), which connects Czech and Slovak research facilities. Join us in pushing the boundaries of research and its application.

Job Description

.....

Key Duties:

- To
- To

Skills and Qualifications

- Ph.D. degree in Plasma Physics (finished not more than eight years ago)
- Experience in
- Good knowledge of English (verbal and written)
- Active and positive approach to work
- Good knowledge of MS Office tools
-

We Offer

- Complex initial training including business trips to cooperating universities (Comenius University in Bratislava, University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, Masaryk University in Brno)
- Stimulating research environment with access to worldwide contacts with specialised measuring equipment
- Collaboration with international partners and opportunities to publish in renowned journals
- Financial support for conferences and workshops on scientific and technical skills and international workshops
- Flexible working hours and occasional home office to support personal needs in family and career compatibility
- Employee benefits such as
- Support with your relocation to Czech / Slovak Republic

Workplace: Department of, Faculty of, University

Type of Contract: temporary position with 1,5 year contract (18 months) with

possible extension, non-academic

Working Hours: 1,0 FTE (full-time employment of 40 hours per week)

Expected Start Date: 1. 10. 2024 or negotiable with respect to immigration timelines for non EU candidates

Number of Open Positions: 2

Pay: CZK ... Gross per month / negotiable

Application Deadline: DD MM YYYY

EU Researcher Profile: R2

Informal **inquiries about the position** can be sent to [redacted], email: [redacted], phone [redacted].

Selection Process

The application shall be **submitted online by 2024 via an e-application**, please find the reference to the e-application in the beginning and end of the advertisement.

The candidate shall provide following:

- CV
- Cover letter describing candidate's research interest and experience
- Summary of research outputs and publications
- Names and contact details of at least 2 references.

Received applications will be considered carefully in line with [principles of the EU Charter and Code for Researchers](#). Selection criteria: (i) meeting qualification requirements described above, (ii) all required documents provided.

Shortlisted candidates will be invited to online interview.

University Recruitment Policy (OTM-R) can be seen [redacted].

About the Workplace

Department of

Faculty of

University

University..... is an equal opportunity employer. We support diversity and are committed to creating an inclusive environment for all employees. Visit our Career page.

We are looking forward to hearing from you!

Attachment 2: The European Competency Framework for Researchers

Detailed text can be found here: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en

MANAGING RESEARCH	Mobilise resources	Identify key relevant funding sources and prepare research grant applications in order to obtain funds and grants. Write research proposals and pitch ideas to convince potential investors (internal or external to the organisation) of the need to fund research initiatives.
	Manage projects	Manage and plan various resources, such as human resources, budget, deadline, results, and quality necessary for a specific project and for a project portfolio and monitor the progress in order to achieve a specific goal within a set time and budget using project management tools.
	Negotiate	Exchange ideas while analysing issues and interests at stake, enabling opposing sides to resolve disputes and reach an agreement, or making decisions to resolve disputes.
	Evaluate research	Reflect on research activities and learn from successes and failures based on personal experience, feedback from others or monitoring and evaluation. Assess proposals, progress, impact and outcomes of peer researchers.
	Promote open access publications	Develop a strategy to publish your research and identify the appropriate publication channel(s) to implement that strategy. Use open publication strategies when possible. Be familiar with the use of information technology to support research, and with the development and management of CRIS (current research information systems) and institutional repositories. Provide licensing and copyright advice, use bibliometric indicators, and measure and report research impact.
MAKING AN IMPACT	Participate in the publication process	Submit, revise and publish academic research through the most appropriate dissemination means and participate in peer review processes, including open peer review.

	Disseminate results to the research community	Publicly disclose research results by any appropriate means, including training, conferences, workshops, colloquia and research publications.
	Teach in academic or vocational contexts	Instruct students in the theory and practice of academic or vocational subjects, transferring the content of own and others' research activities.
	Communicate to the broad public	Communicate about scientific findings to a non-scientific audience, including the general public. Tailor the communication of scientific concepts, debates, findings to the audience, using a variety of methods to different target groups, including visual presentations and various forms of written, spoken and digital communication.
	Increase the impact of Science on Policy and Society	Increase the impact and use of research findings in policy making, by providing input to and maintaining professional relationships with policymakers and other stakeholders.
	Promote open innovation	Apply techniques, models, methods, and strategies that contribute to the promotion of steps towards Innovation through collaboration with external people and organizations.
	Promote the transfer of knowledge	Deploy broad awareness and knowledge of processes of knowledge valorisation aimed to maximise the two-way flow of tools, content material, technology, intellectual property, expertise and capability between the research base and relevant stakeholders within the research field.
SELF-MANAGEMENT	Manage personal professional development	Take responsibility for lifelong learning and continuous professional development. Engage in learning to support and update professional competency and develop personal skills. Identify priority areas for professional development based on reflection about own practice and through contact with peers and stakeholders. Pursue a cycle of self-improvement and develop credible career plans.
	Show entrepreneurial spirit	Demonstrate a proactive mindset and determination to achieve success in business or successfully create it.

	Plan self-organisation	Identify the necessary tasks and prioritise them in order to develop an individual schedule and perform the work in an autonomous way, ensuring that the requirements are met. Understand how to behave and work in a sustainable way, including from the environmental point of view, and be mindful of impact of own activities on the environment.
	Cope with pressure	Handle challenges, disruption, and change and recover from set-backs and adversity
COGNITIVE ABILITIES	Abstract thinking	Demonstrate the ability to use concepts in order to make and understand generalisations, and relate or connect them to other items, events, or experiences.
	Critical thinking	Exercise critical judgement and thinking, develop own assumptions, and establish a way of working based on critical thinking.
	Analytical thinking	Using logic and reasoning to develop alternative solutions, conclusions or approaches to problems and identify their strengths and weaknesses.
	Strategic thinking	Develop a vision to turn ideas into action. Obtain and synthesize information to identify and explore trends, opportunities, threats (also based on intuition and creativity) to achieve a long-term goal and to thrive in a competitive, changing environment. Identify alternative paths to turn ideas into action, select the most appropriate approach and adjust where necessary.
	Systemic thinking	Understand and take account of the characteristics of (inter)national research systems where researchers interact with all relevant stakeholders and of the position of individual researchers and their organisation within the system. Situate research activities within the wider context to improve the understanding of complex issues and identify linkages with related issues.
	Problem solving	Develop and implement solutions to practical, operational or conceptual problems which arise in the execution of work in a wide range of contexts.
	Creativity	Develop several ideas and opportunities to create value, including better solutions to existing and new challenges.

		Explore and experiment with innovative approaches. Combine knowledge and resources to achieve valuable effects.
WORK WITH OTHERS	Interact professionally	Show consideration to others and professional collegial behaviour. Listen, give and receive feedback and respond perceptively to others. Engage effectively and in a goal-directed manner with other people in a professional setting, also involving staff supervision and leadership.
	Develop networks	Develop alliances, contacts or partnerships, and exchange information with others. Foster integrated and open collaborations where different stakeholders co-create shared value research and innovations. Develop your personal profile or brand and make yourself visible and accessible in face-to-face and online networking environments.
	Work in teams	Work confidently within a group with each doing their part in the service of the whole.
	Ensure wellbeing at work	Understand the links between work, physical and mental health and wellbeing. Be adequately informed about health promotion and disease prevention to take responsibility for the personal work situation considering the impact on others to create a healthy work environment.
	Build mentor-mentee relationships	Mentor individuals by providing emotional support, sharing experiences and giving advice to the individual to help them in their personal development, as well as adapting the support and guidance to the specific needs of the individual and heeding their requests and expectations. Vice versa, as a mentee, seek support and advice provided by the mentor.
	Promote inclusion & diversity	Promote and ensure equality and diversity management, in words as well as in actions and conduct. Guide and advise colleagues about how to work in diverse teams and contexts.
MANAGING RESEARCH TOOLS	Manage research data	Produce and analyse research data originating from qualitative and quantitative research methods. Store and maintain the data in research databases. Support the re-use of research data and be familiar with data management principles, including FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and

		Reusable) principles. Make data as open as possible, and as closed as necessary
	Promote citizen science	Engage citizens in scientific and research activities and promote their contribution in terms of knowledge, time or resources invested.
	Manage intellectual property rights	Deal with the private legal rights that protect the products of the intellect from unlawful infringement.
	Operate open-source software	Operate Open-Source software, beyond licensed software, knowing the main Open-Source models, licensing schemes, and the coding practices commonly adopted in the production of Open-Source software.
DOING RESEARCH	Have disciplinary expertise	Demonstrate deep knowledge and complex understanding of a specific research area, including responsible research, research ethics and integrity principles, privacy and GDPR requirements, related to research activities within a specific discipline.
	Perform scientific research	Gain, correct or improve knowledge about phenomena by selecting or developing the appropriate scientific approach and by using scientific methods and research techniques based on empirical or measurable observations.
	Conduct interdisciplinary research	Work and use research findings and data across disciplinary/functional boundaries, including in collaborative settings.
	Write research documents	Draft and edit research, academic or technical texts on different subjects.
	Apply research ethics and integrity principles	Apply fundamental ethical principles and legislation to research and innovation, including issues of research integrity. Perform, review, or report research avoiding misconducts such as fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism.

Attachment 3: COLOSSE Key Competencies Template

Key competencies identified by COLOSSE partners at the Consortium meeting in Bratislava as essential for developing soft skills, transferable skills, including technical and scientific skills, for the following position types:

1. Researchers R1 + R2
2. Support Staff (Research Managers and Research Administrators)

POSITION TYPE 1: Researchers R1 + R2

Competency Categories:

A. Soft Skills

These are interpersonal and communication skills crucial for collaborative work and effective research management.

- Competency 1: **Communication Skills**
 - Ability to present research findings to both academic and non-academic audiences.
 - Ability to communicate science to the public.
 - Ability to write scientific papers, reports, and proposals.
 - Responsibility and reliability.
- Competency 2: **Teamwork and Collaboration**
 - Ability to work effectively in multidisciplinary teams.
 - Competency in networking and building professional relationships.
- Competency 3: **Leadership and Management**
 - Skills in leading research teams and projects.
 - Ability to mentor and guide junior researchers.
- Competency 4: **Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking**
 - Competency in identifying problems and developing creative solutions.
 - Ability to critically assess research data and methodologies.
- Competency 5: **Managing Difficult Situations**
 - Ability to manage and resolve conflicts.
 - Ability to master the art of saying No.
 - Ability to performing well in high-pressure environments.
- Competency 6: **Maintaining Work-life Balance**
 - Ability to effectively manage and harmonize professional responsibilities and personal life.
 - Ability to recognize, prevent, and manage symptoms of burnout.

B. Technical and Scientific Skills

These are core research skills that are essential for R1 and R2 researchers.

- Competency 1: **Use of Research Methods and Techniques**

- Competency in designing experiments and methodologies.
- Ability to apply appropriate research tools and technologies.
- **Competency 2: Data Analysis and Interpretation**
 - Skills in quantitative and qualitative analysis.
 - Proficiency in interpreting research results and drawing conclusions.
- **Competency 3: Scientific Data Lifecycle Management**
 - Ability to manage scientific data throughout its lifecycle (data creation & collection, processing, analysis, preservation, archiving, disposal).
 - Ability to ensure data integrity, accessibility, and compliance with legal and ethical standards
- **Competency 4: Utilization of Specialized Devices, Equipment and Methods**
 - Ability to operate and utilize specialized instruments and equipment.
 - Ability to use specialized methods and techniques relevant to the specific field of research.
 - Ability to apply these methods effectively to address complex research problems.
- **Competency 5: Working with Scientific Results and Publication Practices**
 - Ability to effectively manage, interpret, and apply scientific results.
 - Ability to understand ethical considerations in publishing and master of various publication formats
 - Familiarity with the peer-review process, open access policies, and metrics for evaluating research impact.
- **Competency 6: Knowledge of Open Access, Open Science, and Open Data**
 - Comprehensive understanding of open access, open science, and open data principles.
 - Familiarity with open-access publishing models, data sharing practices, and the ethical implications of making research outputs freely accessible.
 - Ability to access, share, and disseminate research outputs freely, manage and store data in ways that ensure accessibility and compliance with relevant policies and regulations.
- **Competency 7: Research Project & Financial Management**
 - Ability to plan and manage research projects.
 - Knowledge of research funding and grant writing.
 - Proficiency in financial management & budget control.
- **Competency 8: Identification of funding opportunities for research projects**
 - Ability to identify grants, fellowships, and other financial resources, and to evaluate their suitability and alignment with project goals.

C. Transferable Skills

These are skills applicable across different domains and contribute to overall professional development.

- Competency 1: **Time Management**
 - Ability to manage time effectively to meet research deadlines.
 - Ability to prioritize tasks based on urgency and importance.
 - Responsibility and reliability.
- Competency 2: **Adaptability and Flexibility**
 - Ability to adjust to new research environments and changing circumstances.
 - Willingness to learn new skills and adapt to technological advancements.
- Competency 3: **Proficiency in English Language**
 - Adequate command of the English language, both written and spoken, enabling effective communication within international research environments.
 - Ability to understand & produce scientific documents, engage in academic discussions and present research findings to both specialized & general audiences in English language.
- Competency 4: **Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools**
 - Ability to understand principles of AI tools and their applications within research field.
 - Ability to use AI-driven tools for data analysis, simulation, prediction, and other research-related tasks, including the selection of appropriate AI methods and tools for specific research needs.
 - Awareness of ethical considerations and potential biases in AI, ensuring transparency, fairness, and accountability in AI-driven research.
- Competency 5: **Ethical and Social Responsibility**
 - Understanding of research ethics and responsible conduct.
 - Awareness of the societal impact of research.
- Competency 6: **Lifelong Learning**
 - Commitment to continuous personal and professional development.
 - Engagement in training opportunities and professional courses.

POSITION TYPE 2: Support Staff (Research Managers and Research Administrators)

Competency Categories:

A. Soft Skills

These are interpersonal and communication skills crucial for collaborative work and effective research management.

- Competency 1: **Communication Skills**
 - Proficiency in presenting to both academic and non-academic audiences.
 - Ability to write reports, and proposals.
- Competency 2: **Teamwork and Collaboration**
 - Ability to work effectively in multidisciplinary teams.
 - Competency in networking and building professional relationships.
 - Responsibility and reliability.
- Competency 3: **Leadership and Management**
 - Skills in leading teams and projects.
 - Ability to coordinate within the project framework.
 - Ability to mentor and guide junior colleagues.
- Competency 4: **Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking**
 - Competency in identifying problems and developing creative solutions.
- Competency 5: **Managing Difficult Situations**
 - Ability to manage and resolve conflicts.
 - Ability to master the art of saying No.
 - Ability to performing well in high-pressure environments.
- Competency 6: **Maintaining Work-life Balance**
 - Ability to effectively manage and harmonize professional responsibilities and personal life.
 - Ability to recognize, prevent, and manage symptoms of burnout.

B. Technical and Specialized Skills

These are core technical and specialised skills that are essential for Research Managers and Research Administrators.

- Competency 1: **Research Project Management and Administration**
 - Ability to plan and manage research projects.
 - Knowledge of research funding and grant writing.
- Competency 2: **Understanding of Financial Project Management**
 - Ability to understand financial regulations and rules set by grant providers
 - Ability to manage and report financial resources in compliance with their requirements.

- Proficiency in financial management & budget control.
- Competency 3: **Identification of Funding Opportunities for Research Projects**
 - Ability to identify grants, fellowships, and other financial resources.
- Competency 4: **Data Analysis and Interpretation**
 - Skills in quantitative and qualitative analysis.

C. Transferable Skills

These are skills applicable across different domains and contribute to overall professional development.

- Competency 1: **Time Management**
 - Ability to manage time effectively to meet research deadlines.
 - Prioritization of tasks based on urgency and importance.
 - Responsibility and reliability.
- Competency 2: **Adaptability and Flexibility**
 - Competency in adjusting to new research environments and changing circumstances.
 - Willingness to learn new skills and adapt to technological advancements.
- Competency 3: **Proficiency in English Language**
 - Advanced proficiency in both written and spoken English, essential for managing international research projects.
 - Ability to draft formal documents in English (such as grant proposals and reports),
 - Ability to negotiate and collaborate effectively with stakeholders across different countries in English, and lead meetings or presentations with clarity and professionalism.
- Competency 4: **Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools**
 - Ability to understand principles of AI tools and their applications within research management field.
 - Ability to assess and implement AI-driven tools for enhancing project management, resource allocation, performance tracking, and other administrative tasks to support research efficiency and innovation.
 - Awareness of ethical considerations and potential biases in AI use, ensuring data privacy, accountability and promoting transparency and accountability within research practices.
- Competency 5: **Lifelong Learning**
 - Commitment to continuous personal and professional development.
 - Engagement in training opportunities and professional courses.

Attachment 4: COLOSSE Training Need Questionnaire Survey Template

Target Group: Researchers and Research Support Staff

Purpose: To identify specific training needs based on the Competencies identified as necessary for the COLOSSE project.

To be created and processed in MS FORMS

Section 1: General Information

1. Name:

2. Position:

- Researcher (R1)
- Researcher (R2)
- Research Manager
- Research Administrator

3. **Colosse Partner Organisation/**Research Group:

4. Years of Experience in Current Role:

- 0-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 10+ years

Section 2: Competency Assessment

Please rate your level of Competency in the following areas on a scale of 1 to 5 (1 = No experience/knowledge, 5 = Expert level).

Position type 1: Researchers R1 + R2	Position type 2: Support Staff (Research Managers and Research Administrators)
A. <u>Softskills</u>	A. <u>Softskills</u>
Competency 1: Communication Skills	Competency 1: Communication Skills
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5
Competency 2: Teamwork & Collaboration	Competency 2: Teamwork & Collaboration

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 3: **Leadership & Management**

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 4: **Problem-Solving & Critical Thinking**

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 5: **Managing Difficult Situations**

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 6: **Maintaining Work-Life Balance**

1
2
3
4

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 3: **Leadership & Management**

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 4: **Problem-Solving & Critical Thinking**

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 5: **Managing Difficult Situations**

1
2
3
4
5

Competency 6: **Maintaining Work-Life Balance**

1
2
3
4

5

B. Technical and Scientific Skills

Competency 1: **Use of Research Methods & Techniques**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 2: **Data Analysis and Interpretation**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 3: **Scientific Data Lifecycle Management**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 4: **Utilization of Specialized Devices, Equipment and Methods**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 5: **Working with Scientific Results and Publication Practices**

5

B. Technical and Specialized Skills

Competency 1: **Research Project Management and Administration**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 2: **Understanding of Financial Project Management**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 3: **Identification of Funding Opportunities for Research Projects**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 4: **Data Analysis & Interpretation**

1

2

3

4

5

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 6: Knowledge of Open Access, Open Science, and Open Data

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 7: Research Project & Financial Management

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 8: Identification of Funding Opportunities for Research Projects

1

2

3

4

5

C. Transferrable Skills

Competency 1: Time Management

1

2

3

C. Transferrable Skills

Competency 1: Time Management

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 2: **Adaptability & Flexibility**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 3: **Proficiency in English Language**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 4: **Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 5: **Ethical and Social Responsibility**

1

2

3

4

5

4

5

Competency 2: **Adaptability & Flexibility**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 3: **Proficiency in English Language**

1

2

3

4

5

Competency 4: **Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools**

1

2

3

4

5

Section 3: Training Needs Identification

1. In which areas do you feel you need training to perform your role more effectively? (Please select all that apply)

- Communication Skills
- Teamwork & Collaboration
- Leadership & Management
- Problem-Solving & Critical Thinking
- Managing Difficult Situations
- Maintaining Work-Life Balance
- Use of Research Methods & Techniques
- Working with Scientific Results and Publication Practices
- Scientific Writing and Publication
- Knowledge of Open Access, Open Science, and Open Data
- Research Project Management
- Research Project Management and Administration
- Understanding of Financial Project Management
- Identification of Funding Opportunities for Research Projects
- Time Management
- Adaptability & Flexibility
- Proficiency in English Language
- Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools
- Ethical and Social Responsibility
- Other (Please specify): _____

2. Please describe any specific training topics or areas that you believe would benefit you and your work:

Section 4: Additional Comments

Please provide any additional feedback or suggestions for the prepared training program:

Thank you for your participation!

Your input is valuable in shaping a training program that meets the needs of all staff and supports the success of the **COLOSSE** project.

Attachment 5: COLOSSE Training Topics Template

Position Type 1: Researchers R1 + R2

- **Proposed Training Topic 1:** [Insert specific training topic here]

Competency / Training Need Addressed 1: This topic is designed to enhance [insert specific competency or skill] critical for [current or future role-specific task/goal].

- **Proposed Training Topic 2:** [Insert specific training topic here]

Competency / Training Need Addressed 2: This training will address [insert specific gap in knowledge or skill], helping researchers to [explain the relevance to their role].

Position Type 2: Support Staff (Research Managers and Research Administrators)

- **Proposed Training Topic 1:** [Insert specific training topic here]

Competency / Training Need Addressed 1: This topic will develop [insert specific competency or skill] essential for supporting research activities and enhancing operational efficiency.

- **Proposed Training Topic 2:** [Insert specific training topic here]

Competency / Training Need Addressed 2: This training focuses on [insert specific skill or area of knowledge], ensuring that support staff are equipped to [explain how this training supports their duties or the research environment].

Attachment 6: COLOSSE Career Development Plan Template

1. Personal and Professional Information

- Name: [Insert Name]
- Position: [Researcher / Research Manager]
- Department/Institute: [Insert Department Name]
- Supervisor/Manager: [Insert Supervisor/Manager Name]
- Date: [Insert Date]

2. Career Objectives

- [Objective 1]
- [Objective 2]
- [Objective 3]

3. Current Competencies and Skills

Soft Skills:

- [Competency 1]
- [Competency 2]
- [Competency 3]

Managerial Competencies (for Research Managers):

- [Competency 1]
- [Competency 2]
- [Competency 3]

Technical and Scientific Skills:

- [Skill 1]
- [Skill 2]
- [Skill 3]

Transferable Skills:

- [Skill 1]
- [Skill 2]
- [Skill 3]

4. Skills and Competencies Development

Identified Gaps:

- [Gap 1]
- [Gap 2]
- [Gap 3]

Training and Development Activities:

- Training 1: [Description, Timeline, and Provider]
- Training 2: [Description, Timeline, and Provider]
- Training 3: [Description, Timeline, and Provider]

Mentorship/Coaching:

- Mentor/Coach Name: [Insert Name]
- Focus Area: [Insert Focus Area]
- Timeline: [Insert Timeline]

5. Research/Project Activities

Current Research Projects:

- Project Title: [Insert Title]
- Role/Contribution: [Insert Role]
- Expected Outcomes: [Insert Outcomes]

Future Research Projects/Ideas:

- Project Title/Idea: [Insert Title/Idea]
- Proposed Role: [Insert Role]
- Expected Impact: [Insert Impact]

6. Networking and Collaboration

Key Contacts/Collaborators:

- [Collaborator 1]
- [Collaborator 2]
- [Collaborator 3]

Conferences/Seminars/Workshops:

- Event 1: [Name, Date, and Location]
- Event 2: [Name, Date, and Location]
- Event 3: [Name, Date, and Location]

7. Milestones and Review

Milestone 1:

- Target Date: [Insert Date]
- Objective: [Insert Objective]
- Status: [Not Started / In Progress / Completed]

Milestone 2:

- Target Date: [Insert Date]
- Objective: [Insert Objective]
- Status: [Not Started / In Progress / Completed]

Milestone 3:

- Target Date: [Insert Date]
- Objective: [Insert Objective]
- Status: [Not Started / In Progress / Completed]
- Review Date: [Insert Date for Next Review]

8. Approval and Signatures

Researcher/Research Manager:

- Name: [Insert Name]
- Signature: [Insert Signature]
- Date: [Insert Date]

Supervisor/Manager:

- Name: [Insert Name]
- Signature: [Insert Signature]
- Date: [Insert Date]

Attachment 7: COLOSSE Training Feedback Form

To be created using the MS Forms application and sent to participants after attending the training.

COLOSSE Workshop Name:

Date:

Dear colleagues,

Thank you for attending the workshop. We would like to gain your feedback on this event.

Your answers will help us to further improve the educational activities organised by the COLOSSE partners. Thank you for your time, we much appreciate your reply.

* Mandatory

1. Are you satisfied with the quality of the information you learned at the workshop? *

- Yes
- Partially
- No

2. Will you use the knowledge you have gained from the workshop in your practice? *

- Yes
- Partially
- No

3. Your satisfaction with the lecturer: *

Please rate using the scale: 1=the lowest score, 5=the highest score

	1 (highest)	2	3	4	5 (highest)
Training style	<input type="radio"/>				
Expert knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
Understandable and clear talk	<input type="radio"/>				

4. Your overall satisfaction with the workshop: *

Please rate using the scale: 1=the lowest score, 5=the highest score

	1 (highest)	2	3	4	5 (highest)
To what extent did the training meet your expectations?	<input type="radio"/>				
Your opinion on the overall level of the workshop	<input type="radio"/>				
The organisation of the workshop.	<input type="radio"/>				

5. What has been the most valuable part of the program to you?

6. Has there been any information/topic you missed at the workshop?